

ROLE OF STRATEGIC LEADERSHIP IN APPLYING TOTAL QUALITY MANAGEMENT A FIELD STUDY IN PRIVATE HOSPITALS IN THE CAPITAL, SANA'A

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Abstract

Total quality management has gained extensive prominence over the last few decades and continues to play a significant role in modern healthcare delivery. This study aimed to measure the role of strategic leadership in applying TQM in private hospitals in the capital Sana'a. Cross-sectional study was adopted. The research sample included (230) employees in senior administrative positions at six hospitals. To achieve the aim of the research, a questionnaire was used to collect data related to the research variables. The data was analyzed using statistical software (SPSS) to obtain the results. The current study found a positive correlation and role between the practice of strategic leadership in the application of total quality management, and it was found that there is a varying positive role for the dimensions of strategic leadership in the application of total quality management, there was the most role the strategic orientation and the least role is the human capital development. The current study contributes to the literature by showing the concepts and dimensions of strategic leadership and total quality management. This study is also the first to analyze the role of strategic leadership in the application of total quality management in the health sector in Yemen. The study shows the important role of strategic leadership in the application of total quality management, which is reflected in the success and development of private hospitals.

Keywords: Strategic Leadership, Strategic Direction, Total Quality Management, Private Hospitals.

INTRODUCTION

Any organization's prosperity is based on its leadership. Leaders are those who can overcome obstacles and make choices in the most challenging situations. Strategic leadership is a concept that has evolved from traditional leadership as a result. Strategic change can lead to organizational adaptation and harmony in light of the demands of globalization and its numerous and complex effects, making strategic leadership one of the fundamental sources and resources that the organization uses to achieve competitive advantage (Jad Al-Rub, 2012, p. 47). Total quality management (TQM) is a deeply ingrained notion that has been identified and is acknowledged as being crucial for the direction and analysis of problems with corporate quality and productivity. (Alsughayir, 2016, p. 656). This necessitates coming up with new ways to replace outdated procedures and methods as well as providing suitable and adaptable ways to respond to them. This made contemporary institutions seriously consider their ownership of a source of strength and an efficient engine for other resources that they possess, and only by implementing overall quality management through (senior management dedication to customer focus, staff participation, and continuous improvement) would this be possible. Private hospitals' top priority is the quality of their medical care, and as a result, thorough quality control has emerged as one of their most crucial fundamental functions. Numerous studies, including one by Razi et al. (2023), have looked at the role of strategic leadership in the implementation of comprehensive quality management in various enterprises. This study sought to

understand how effective leadership contributes to the adoption of total quality management principles and practices. By highlighting the significance of leadership in fostering a culture of quality and continuous improvement, the study's findings are helpful to practitioners and organizations looking to improve their quality management efforts. According to a (2019) Conneer-Boyd study To better understand the diversity of health options available in the United States of America, a study was conducted. Major conclusions of the study: Data analysis identified seven themes: client satisfaction, leadership factor, human capital development, choice, and healthcare counseling in Georgia may favor a catalyst for social change by enhancing healthcare selectivity in the United States, and promoting employment growth. the generation of jobs. Puri et al.'s (2019) study sought to determine the process for implementing overall quality management in the hospital sector and understand how it relates to controlling hospital performance. The findings showed that total quality management and its effect on managing hospital performance are positively correlated, according to a (2019) study by Al-Qawasmeh and Al-Marri The Qatari Ministry of Commerce and Industry was used as a case study in the study to identify the administrative leadership in the application of overall quality management principles. The Qatari Ministry of Commerce and Industry is comprehensive in its facets (customer focus, continuous improvement, employee empowerment, and senior management commitment). A study by Joesem and Hussein (2018) sought to understand the role of administrative leadership at the University of Babylon in supporting and putting total quality management principles into practice, as well as the extent to which there are statistically significant differences in the leaders' responses to that question. The study's most significant finding was that leadership and management have a significant role in supporting and putting overall quality management principles into practice at the University of Babylon as well as Study Ayedh (2013)The goal of the study was to determine the relationship between the level of overall quality management implementation in the hospital and the administrative leadership's contribution to that implementation at the University of Science and Technology Hospital. at the hospital run by Yemen's University of Science and Technology. For a variety of reasons, including growing competition among them and elevated patient and hospital auditor expectations, commercial companies, including private hospitals in Yemen, have grown more interested in the topic of quality. Based on the aforementioned, this study aims to provide a thorough understanding of the concept of the role of strategic leadership in the application of total quality management in all of its dimensions, in a manner that suits the stage and achieves the study's desired objectives, in the chosen environment of the Yemeni private hospitals in the nation's capital, Sana'a. This is done through a field study to produce results and recommendations that can be used. on both a theoretical and practical level in the setting under study.

LITERATURE REVIEW

A: Strategic Leadership

By implementing a strategic shift that will allow total quality management to be applied to the hospital, top management must be able to analyze the future of hospitals through vision and the use of competencies and guide them toward strategic goals. Using pertinent citations, the following paragraph will provide an outline of strategic leadership and its key elements: Strategic leadership is at the core of strategic

management, and as such, the amount to which it is effective at the top of the organization in particular and at all levels generally determines the success of strategic management in meeting its goals (Hitt & Ireland, 2002, p. 4). The capacity for strategic leadership is the capacity to foresee, maintain flexibility, and enable others to implement strategic change as required. Strategic leadership is multifunctional and requires working with people, overseeing a complete organization rather than a single functional department, and adjusting to ongoing change (Hitt et al, 2008, p. 340). The ability to foresee, motivate, and retain the flexibility of others to make desirable strategic adjustments is referred to as strategic leadership. Strategic leadership involves all of an organization's human resources since it is multifunctional (Gintings et al., 2021, p. 1506). The first practice of strategic leadership is the strategic direction defined. This is the ability of the strategic leader to see the future of the organization in a clear and integrated manner. Applying these practices will increase the application of total quality management (Rahima, 2012, p. 253). The ability of an organization to manage its activities in a way that confirms competitive advantages by providing customers with better value for their money than rivals by investing in people and the organization's abilities to achieve high standards of production is known as its core capabilities (Naif, 2007, p. 50). The third strategic leadership practice is building human capital, which is the most crucial integrated resource of all. Increasing income, life satisfaction, and social cohesiveness inside the institution are important. The knowledge, skills, and capabilities of people make up human capital (Hitt & Ireland, 2002, p. 4). Human capital is the understanding that people inside a company or organization are a crucial asset that contributes to growth and development, much like tangible assets like equipment and cash do (Hili et al., 2017, p. 481). Organizational culture is the fourth strategic leadership practice. It is a set of beliefs, symbols, and basic values that all members of the company share and that have an impact on how the organization carries out its tasks (Dahish, 2017, p.1139). The sixth strategic leadership practice is to continue organizational operations or change their patterns, managers must follow certain procedures, which help the organization adapt to changing environmental conditions. To accomplish the unique strategic aim of the organization, the competent leader strikes a balance between financial and strategic control (Al-Faihan & Jallab, 2006, p. 8). The sixth practice of strategic leadership is the ethical practice, which is the collection of moral guidelines, beliefs, and standards that direct action in terms of what is right or wrong, good or bad. (Daft, 2000, p. 35).

B: Total quality management (TQM)

Complete quality control is An organizational philosophy that has the support of senior management, is based on employee engagement, seeks long-term success through client satisfaction, and is continued in the continual enhancement of work performance in hospitals. With the use of pertinent sources, this paragraph will give an outline of TQM and its essential elements. It has been determined that the theory behind improving services and output in enterprises is total quality management (TQM) (Al-Shabibi, 2019, p. 46). Total Quality Management (TQM) is a management-based strategy that involves all team members in enhancing an organization's procedures, goods, and culture to increase customer and other stakeholder satisfaction (Sin & Jusoh, 2019, p. 339). The goal of total quality management (TQM) is to raise the caliber of all products and services. TQM encourages employee involvement, customer satisfaction as a priority, and ongoing improvement (Khan et al., 2023, p. 322). TQM It is possible to claim that activity, objective, and management all work

effectively along with the quality policy, purpose, and responsibility as well as the application of quality management techniques (Kusumawati, 2020, p. 2577). There is no agreement between scientists and researchers on the number of original principles of total quality management, some of them said that there are 5, some said 10 principles and others said 15. According to the points of view, many researchers reach their conclusions. The basic principles of total quality management are the commitment of senior leadership, quality work, quality work policy, training, employee participation, teamwork, customer focus, quality information, supplier management, continuous improvement, operations management, strategic planning for quality, assessment performance, service design, organizational culture, internal customer satisfaction, and social responsibility. For organizations to enjoy success, they must only apply the principles of total quality management (Essel, 2020, p. 31). The first practice of total quality management is senior management commitment. Top management support reflects the important role of management in driving organization-wide efforts of quality management. Applying total quality management in this study will increase the achievement of competitive advantage (Abuzaid, 2015, p. 88). Defined senior management commitment: Senior management must pay attention to work on enhancing the quality of goods and services offered, and it also means that senior management should be aware of what the application of total quality management will achieve in terms of rationalization, boosted earnings, and availability of support for the organization, then assisting the continuation of its success (Lahabib, 2019, p. 132). Employee involvement is the second TQM practice, and it entails policies that empower staff members to continuously improve how the business runs as well as policies that encourage them to suggest improvements (Abuzaid, 2015, p. 89). TQM's core principles are employee engagement and empowerment. It fosters staff members' active participation in decision-making and problem-solving procedures because it recognizes that they are the primary force behind quality improvement (Dale et al., 2007, p. 207). The third TQM practice, customer orientation, illustrates how much a business considers customer feedback while making quality changes (Abuzaid, 2015, p. 88). The fourth TQM practice, continuous improvement, is defined as a method to reduce production costs and raise quality using physical streams and advanced data (Ahmed & Siddiqui, 2020, p. 9). also defining constant improvement Since quality is characterized as a process rather than a program, the system's viability depends heavily on ongoing systemic questioning. To accomplish their function, processes must always be updated and made simpler, and unnecessary activity must be eliminated. Additionally, involving the customer and the employees in the process of development to regularly use the stages and procedures in their best forms is the greatest way to create a system that is constantly developing. (Halis et al., 2017, p. 20).

METHOD

The population for this study consists of leaders working in private hospitals in the capital Sana'a, where the hospitals that meet the criteria to be a study population are (6) hospitals, which are the private hospitals that have an (A) rating according to their arrangement: (University of Science and Technology Hospital, Azal Hospital, Al-Yaman Al-Saeed Hospital, Modern European Hospital, Dr. Abd al-Qader al-Mutawakel Hospital, Modern German Hospital), Based on the implementation of the comprehensive quality system through quality departments, administrations, and its numerous programs, it received an evaluation (A) from the Yemeni Ministry of Health

that is a percentage higher than 90%. The study used the method of careful enumeration for each member of the community, as it resulted in (251) people from all high administrative and medical staff and recovered (230) people, Strategic leadership was evaluated using the questionnaire, and whole quality management procedures were assessed. Suitable statistical techniques were used to analyze the data that had been collected. The responses were compiled using an analytical descriptive approach, which also gave a general summary of the sample's characteristics. Correlation, variance, and regression analyses were employed as deductive statistical techniques to assess the impact of strategic leadership on the implementation of comprehensive quality management. The statistical package (SPSS) was used for data analysis.

COGNITIVE MODEL OF THE STUDY

Figure 1: It is a Clear Cognitive Model of the Study

RESULTS

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of the Participants

Variable		N	%
Gender	Male	156	67.83
	Female	74	32.17
Age	30 years and under	54	23.48
	31-40 years	144	62.61
	41-50 years	32	13.91
Educational Level	High School	48	20.87
	Bachelor's Degree	134	58.62
	Master's Degree	38	16.52
	Doctorate	10	4.35
Total		230	100.00

The demographic details of the participants are shown in the table. Among the 230 employees in the sample, 156 (67.83%) are male and 74 (32.17%) are female. The bulk of participants (62.61%), in terms of age categories, are between the ages of 31 and 40. In terms of educational attainment, the majority (58.62%) have a bachelor's degree.

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics of Strategic Leadership Factor

Dimension	Mean	SD
Strategic direction	6.20	0.88
Maintain core capabilities	5.90	1.13
Human capital development	5.57	1.36
Organizational culture	5.55	1.23
Balanced regulatory oversight	5.79	1.07
Ethical practices	1.26	1.26
Average	5.79	1.05

The previous table demonstrated that private hospitals generally practiced "strategic leadership" at a high level, with an arithmetic mean of (5.79), a standard deviation of (1.05), and a rate of (82.71%). This outcome, according to the researchers, is due to their interest in the strategic direction through the creation of plans for private hospitals (the study's subject), which have goals, a clear vision, a clear mission, and aim to maintain human resources with high efficiency and infrastructure with cutting-edge technology. It also cares about training programs for all employees. Hospital leadership is interested in organizational and financial oversight, actual performance monitoring, and high-end ethical behavior to provide high-quality service, Employee incentives, teamwork incentives, and decision-making incentives are used to do this, improving each hospital's competitive performance. With an arithmetic mean of (6.20) and a standard deviation of (0.88), the "strategic direction" was the highest dimension of strategic leadership in the first place. Its objectives, mission, and long-term vision support the use of overall quality management. In terms of response, the "organizational culture" dimension was placed last with an arithmetic mean of (5.55) and a standard deviation of (1.23). The lack of interest in "organizational culture" is attributed to dissatisfaction with how hospitals are using organizational culture to strengthen leadership, promote organizational justice and transparency, and support decision-making.

Table 3: Descriptive Statistics of Application of Total Quality Management Factor

Dimension	Mean	SD
Senior management commitment	5.94	1.10
Focus on the customer	5.92	1.11
Employee participation	5.57	1.33
Continuous improvement	5.71	1.18
Average	5.79	1.12

With an arithmetic mean of (5.79) and a standard deviation of (1.12) in terms of response, it is evident from the previous table that the level of application of "Total Quality Management" in private hospitals (field of research) as a whole was at a high level. and the outcome shows that senior management in private hospitals is committed to upholding the principles of total quality management, including customer focus, being the first to respond to customers' needs, employee participation in the accomplishment of challenging tasks, and efforts to enhance work performance.

With an arithmetic mean of (5.94) and a standard deviation of (1.10) for the "Senior Management Commitment" dimension, and a mean of (5.57) and a standard deviation of (1.33) for the "Employee Participation" dimension, respectively, in last place, a ratio that shows there is a high level of confidence in the study sample and senior management's commitment to applying the principles of total quality management due to the presence of an element of belief in it, but employee participation came in last place due to the lack of encouraging employee participation in coming up with ideas and making decisions and not taking into account their observations, and it is necessary to encourage employee participation.

Hypotheses Testing

A. Testing the Main Hypothesis

The main hypothesis states that "There is a statistically significant role for the strategic leadership in applying total quality management in private hospitals in the capital, Sana'a".

The key hypothesis (effect of strategic leadership on implementing total quality management) was examined using simple linear regression, as shown in Table 4.

Table 4: Model Estimation Between Strategic Leadership And Total Quality Management

Independent variable	Path	Dependent variable	R ²	Beta	T	P-Value
Strategic leadership	-->	Total quality management	0.744	0.922	25.775	0.000

It is evident from the previous table that strategic leadership plays a statistically significant role (R² = 0.744), which means that strategic leadership accounts for a high percentage of the change in the application of total quality management (74.4%) while only (25.6%) of the change is attributable to other factors. Since the study did not address additional factors, the study's main hypothesis was accepted.

B. Testing the Sub-Hypotheses

Testing the sub-hypotheses was performed as follows:

- The first sub-hypothesis states that: "there is a statistically significant role for the strategic direction in applying total quality management in private hospitals in the capital, Sana'a".
- The second sub-hypothesis states that: "there is a statistically significant role for preserving the core capabilities in the application of total quality management in private hospitals in the capital, Sana'a".
- The third sub-hypothesis states that: "there is a statistically significant role for the development of human capital in the application of total quality management in private hospitals in the capital, Sana'a".
- The fourth sub-hypothesis states that: "there is a statistically significant role for organizational culture in the application of total quality management in private hospitals in the capital, Sana'a".
- The fifth sub-hypothesis states that: "there is a statistically significant role for balanced organizational control in the application of comprehensive quality management in Yemeni private hospitals in the capital, Sana'a".

- The sixth sub-hypothesis states that: "there is a statistically significant role to confirm ethical practices in the application of total quality management in private hospitals in the capital, Sana'a".

The impact of strategic leadership aspects on implementing comprehensive quality management was examined using multiple linear regression, as shown in Table 5.

Table 5: Model Estimation between Independent Variables and Total quality management

Independent variable	Path	Dependent variable	Beta	T	P-Value
Strategic direction	-->	Total quality management	0.128	1.789	.075
Maintain core capabilities	-->	Total quality management	0.243	3.377	.001
Human capital development	-->	Total quality management	0.209	2.938	.004
Organizational culture	-->	Total quality management	0.064	0.850	.396
Balanced regulatory oversight	-->	Total quality management	0.116	1.719	.087
Ethical practices	-->	Total quality management	0.280	4.281	.000

The relative significance of the independent variables, which are integrated as follows, was also demonstrated by the regression coefficients in the implementation of total quality management. Whereas the outcomes indicated that the effect rate (beta) value was equal to (0.243, 0.209, 0.280), respectively, and the importance level was (0.001, 0.004, 0.000), and they were both less than the level of significance (0.05), demonstrating that strategic leadership has three dimensions (maintaining core competencies, developing human capital, and emphasizing ethical practices), which together account for (73.2%) of the impact of total quality management in private hospitals. Consequently, the second, third, and fourth sub-hypotheses are accepted.

Concerning the control, organizational culture, and strategic direction dimensions. If these factors come into play, their influence is minimal. Consequently, the impact of the strategic direction is not significant (.075), the organizational culture is not significant (.396), balanced organizational control is not significant (.087), and the impact of total quality management is not significantly impacted by any of these factors (strategic direction, organizational culture, balanced organizational control).

DISCUSSION

The results of testing the main hypothesis indicated that there is a statistically significant effect of strategic leadership in applying total quality management in private hospitals in the capital, Sana'a. This result is consistent with other studies conducted in different environments, including the study (Razi et al., 2023) that benefits practitioners and organizations in the role of leadership in creating a culture of quality and continuous improvement. and study (Ezzeddine, 2019), which demonstrated the existence of a statistically significant role for leadership in the application of total quality management in the Financial Investment Bank in Sudan.

The study (Al-Qawasma and Al-Marri, 2019) confirmed the existence of a statistically significant effect of leadership administrative leadership in the application of total quality management in the Qatari Ministry of Commerce and Industry, and the study (Joesem and Hussein, 2018), which confirmed the existence of a statistically significant correlation for administrative leadership in the application of total quality management at the University of Babylon, and the study (Al-Hadrawi and Hadi, 2018) confirmed the presence of a significant effect For strategic leadership on customer

satisfaction at the Kufa Cement Factory in Iraq, and the study (Al-Matari, 2016), which proved that there is a statistically significant correlation for the role of administrative leadership in the application of total quality management in the National Anti-Corruption Authority in Yemen, and the study (Ayed, 2013), which confirmed the existence of a strong correlation with statistical significance between the role of administrative leadership in The application of total quality management in the University of Science and Technology Hospital in Sana'a.

The researchers attribute this role to the basic role of the strategic leadership in applying total quality management in private hospitals (the field of study) through the interest in developing a future strategic plan concerned with the application of total quality management in private hospitals, and the participation of employees in decision-making through its application of organizational culture and provision of services.

High quality through balanced organizational oversight and training of its human resources, customer satisfaction through application of ethical practices and emphasis on them, outstanding performance by preserving highly qualified human resources and having an infrastructure that achieves its objectives by preserving core capabilities, Through the results of this study, the great interest of private hospitals (the field of study) is noted in the exercise of strategic leadership for the application of total quality management.

CONCLUSION

According to the results of the reviewed study, several conclusions were drawn:

1. There is a great interest among the civil authorities (field of study) regarding strategic leadership, as they plan for their future and leadership vision.
2. The highest practice of strategic leadership in private hospitals (the field of study) was in the dimensions of strategic orientation and core capabilities, and the lowest practice was in the dimensions of organizational culture.
3. There is a great interest among private hospitals (field of study) in total quality management, as it is concerned with the desires and requirements of the client.
4. The highest innovative application in total quality in private hospitals (field of study) was after the commitment of senior management and focus on the client, and the lowest application was in the dimension of employee participation.
5. There is a positive role for the farthest strategic dimension in the application of total quality management in health hospitals (field of study).
6. There is a varying positive role for the dimensions of strategic leadership in the application of total quality management, the most important role is maintaining the core capabilities, and the least important role is the organizational culture.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the conclusions reached, the following recommendations were made:

1. Continuing the practices of strategic leadership in private hospitals (field of study), and promoting practice using modern scientific methods to achieve the goals of hospitals.
2. Increasing interest in the application of total quality management in private hospitals (field of study), and encouraging hospital management to involve employees in decision-making.
3. The need to prepare future leaders in private hospitals through the development of human resources, and attention to their rehabilitation and training, as they are the basis of institutions and their main capital.
4. Encouraging hospital management workers in private hospitals (field of study) to use innovative methods to improve work performance.
5. Preserving the positive role between the strategic leadership in the application of total quality management, and strengthening the role between them more because of its positive impact in achieving positive competition in private hospitals (field of study).

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References

- 1) Al-Feehan, E. A. & Jallab, I. D. 2006. Strategic leadership practices and their relationship to customer service: an analytical study of the opinions of a sample of private bank managers. *Journal of Management and Economics*, (59), 1-32.
- 2) Al-Hadrawi, H. K. & Hadi, J. F. (2018). Strategic leadership practices as a roadmap for achieving customer stability. *Al-Ghary Journal of Economic and Administrative Sciences*, 15 (3), 222-243. (In Arabic)
- 3) Al-Matari, W. Y. M. (2016). *The role of administrative leadership in the possibility of applying total quality management in the National Anti-Corruption Authority*. Master Thesis, Arab Academy for Banking and Financial Sciences, Yemen. (In Arabic)
- 4) Al-Qawasmeh, F. M., & Al-Marri, T. T. (2019). The impact of administrative leadership in applying the principles of total quality management: Qatar Ministry of Commerce and Industry. *Journal of Economics and International Business*, 7 (3), 258-285. <http://doi.org/10.31559/GJEB2019.7.3.2> (In Arabic)
- 5) Al-Shabibi, F. A. A. (2019). Total quality management performance in Omani small and medium enterprises (SMES). *Humanities & Social Sciences Reviews*, 7 (2), 45-57. <https://doi.org/10.18510/hssr.2019.726>
- 6) Alsughayir, A. (2016). Regulatory Role of TQM between the Marketing Orientation, Entrepreneurial Orientation and the Organizational Performance and Competitiveness. *American Journal of Industrial and Business Management*, 6(5), 655-664. <http://doi.org/10.4236/ajibm.2016.65061>
- 7) Abuzaid, A. N. (2015). Examination the impact of total quality management practices in achieving strategic agility: Applied study on the Jordanian private hospitals. *European Journal of Business and Management*, 7(27), 87-96.

- 8) Ahmed, S. W., & Siddiqui, D. A. (2020). Human resource management, total quality management and competitive advantages: Evidence from Pakistani banking industry. *Human Resource Research, 4*(1), 1- 45. <https://doi.org/10.5296/hrr.v4i1.16410>
- 9) Ayed, A. M. M. (2013). The role of administrative leadership in the University of Science and Technology Hospital in applying total quality management. *Arab Journal of Quality Assurance in University Education, 6* (11), 95-141. (In Arabic)
- 10) Conneer-Boyd, J C. (2019). *The Role of Strategic Leadership in Healthcare Profitability*, Walden Dissertations and Doctoral Studies, Walden University.
- 11) Daft, R. L. (2000). *Management*. (5th ed.), The Dryden Press, Harcoyrt College Publishers, USA.
- 12) Dahish, Z. K. J. (2017). Strategic leadership practices and their role in enhancing socialMcapital, a field study in the Directorate of Youth and Sports in Najaf Governorate. *Al-Ghary Journal of Economic and Administrative Sciences,14* (3), 1127-1153. (In Arabic)
- 13) Dale, B., van der Wiele, T., & van Iwaarden, J. (2007). *Managing quality* (5th ed.). Hoboken, NJ: John Wiley & Sons.
- 14) Essel, R. E. (2020). Assessing total quality management (TQM) effect on hospital performance in Ghana using a non-probabilistic approach: The case of Greater Accra Regional Hospital (GARH). *Metamorphosis, 19*(1), 29-41. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0972622520949091>
- 15) Ezzedine, B. Y. A. (2019). *The Role of Leadership in Implementing Total Quality Management and Achieving Competitive Advantage: A Case Study of the Financial Investment Bank*. Master Thesis, Deanship of Development and Quality, Sudan University of Science and Technology. (In Arabic)
- 16) Gad Alrb, S. M. (2012). *Strategic leadership. First edition, Cairo, Egypt*, Egyptian Book House. (In Arabic)
- 17) Gintings, S., Sudiadhita, K., Susita, D. (2021) Competitive Advantage As A Mediator on the Influence of Strategic Leadership, DynamicCapabilities, And Knowledge Management ON Organizational, Performance in PT ELNUSA TBK, *PalArch,s Journal of Archaeology of Egypt, Egyptology 18* (7), 1499-1524.
- 18) Halis, M., Twati, M. R., & Halis, M. (2017). Total quality management implementation in the healthcare industry: Findings from Libya. *Management Issues in Healthcare System, 3*(1), 4-21. <http://doi.org/10.33844/MIHS.2017.60466>
- 19) Hili, P., Gani M., Hamzah N., & Rahman Z. (2017). Effect of human capital and leadership on institutions performance and competitive advantages. *International Journal of Management & Social Sciences, 7*(3), 479-488. <http://doi.org/10.21013/jmss.v7.n3.p9>
- 20) Hitt, M. A.& Ireland, R. D. & Hoskission, R. E. (2008). *Strategic management: Competitiveness & Globalizatio*, (8th ed.). South-western College Publishing.
- 21) Hitt, M. A.& Ireland, R. D. (2002). The Essence of Strategic Leadership Managing Human and Social Capital, *Journal of Leadership & Organization Studies, 9* (1), 3-14. <https://doi.org/10.1177/107179190200900101>
- 22) Joycem, M. H., & Hussein, O. (2018). The role of administrative leadership in the application of total quality management: an applied study at the University of Babylon. *Journal of the College of Administration and Economics for Economic, Administrative and Financial Studies, 10* (3), 356-381. (In Arabic)
- 23) Khan, M., Riaz, A., Manzoor, F., Sarwar, K., Hafeez, H., Masood, A., Kumbher, I., & Naseem, A. (2023). The Impact of Total Quality Management (TQM) on Employee Motivation and Job Satisfaction. *Palarch's Journal of Archaeology of Egypt/Egyptology, 20*(2), 319-329.
- 24) Kusumawati, E. (2020). Leadership in Total Quality Management for Service Quality. *In Proceedings of the 1st International Conference on Recent Innovations (ICR 2018)*, p 2576-2582. <https://doi.org/10.5220/0009948625762582>
- 25) Lahabib, B. (2019). *Total Quality Management Concept - Fundamentals - Application Conditions*. Cairo, Egypt: Modern Academy for University Books. (In Arabic)

- 26) Naif, A. K. (2007) . *The relationship between knowledge management and core ability and its impact on strategic performance*. (Doctoral dissertation), Department of Business Administration, University of Baghdad, Iraq.
<http://thesis.mandumah.com/Record/106028/Details> (In Arabic)
- 27) Puri, G., Babu, H., & Sharm, R. (2019). Total Quality Management Implementation in Healthcare Sector, Its Impact on Performance of Hospitals. *International, Journal of Recent Technology and Engineering*, 8(4), 3704-3711. <http://doi.org/10.35940/ijrte.D7968.118419>
- 28) Rahima, S. H. (2012). The role of strategic leadership in preparing for work pressures, an analytical study of the opinions of a sample of military leaders, *Anbar Journal of Administrative and Economic Sciences*, 9 (4), 245-274.
<http://doi.org/10.34009/0782-004-009-014> (In Arabic)
- 29) Riaz, A., Khan, M., Manzoor, F., Kumbher, I., Hafeez, H., Masood, A., Abubakar, M., & Naseem, A. (2023). The role of leadership in the successful implementation of total quality management (TQM). *Palarch's Journal of Archaeology of Egypt/Egyptology*, 20(2), 330-345.
- 30) Sin, K. Y., & Jusoh, M. S. (2019). Identifying and Prioritizing Research Gaps in Studies related to Total Quality Management on Competitive Advantage in Malaysian Hotel Industries. *International Journal of Academic Research Business and Social Sciences*, 9(5), 335–349.
<http://doi.org/10.6007/IJARBS/v9-i5/5875>